

RELATIONS BETWEEN CHEMICAL ACTIVITY AND ABSORPTION IN THE ULTRAVIOLET OF CERTAIN ORGANIC MOLECULES. PART V. THE INTERACTION OF ATOXYL WITH THE HALOGEN DERIVATIVES OF SUBSTITUTED AMIDES OF MALONIC ACID

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Atoxyl is found to be inactive towards chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid. It easily reacts with the bromo derivatives.

In this part it is proposed to study the reactivity of the chlorine atoms substituted in place of the hydrogens of the reactive methylene group ($-CCl_2-$), with regard to atoxyl. It is known that chloroacetamide and its simpler alkyl derivatives condense readily with atoxyl (Jacobs and Heidelberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 2668). Morgan and Walton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 140, 1743) condensed malonyl chloride with *p*-aminophenylarsonic acid.

It has been observed that even under varying experimental conditions atoxyl does not react with the chloro derivatives of the substituted amides of malonic acid of the type (I). This could be attributed to the comparative inactivity or lesser lability of chlorine atoms towards atoxyl.

(I)

(II)

On the other hand the bromine atom substituting the hydrogen of the reactive methylene group ($-CHBr-$) reacts with atoxyl easily. This could be attributed to the fact that bromine atoms are comparatively labile than similarly situated chlorine atoms. For this purpose the following compounds have been selected.

(1) Monobromomalon-di-*p*-bromoanilide. (2) Monobromomalon-di-*p*-tolylamide. (3) Monobromomalon-dibenzylamide.

It has been found that these compounds react with atoxyl forming compounds of the type (III).

It may be pointed that a study has been made of the compounds of the type, $p\text{-H}_2\text{O}_2\text{As} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH} \cdot \text{CH} : (\text{CONHR})_2$, by Lewis and Bent (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 949; Kennedy, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2781).

The resultant compounds, when treated with ice-cold sodium nitrite and hydrochloric acid and alkaline β -naphthol, give the characteristic nitroso reaction indicating the presence of the ($=\text{NH}$) imino grouping in the molecule.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Interaction of Monobromomalon-di-p-bromoanilide with Atoxyl.—2.3 G. of monobromomalon-di-*p*-bromoanilide, m.p. 236° (1 mol.), were dissolved in 50 c.c. of ethyl alcohol to which 1.7 g. of atoxyl (1 mol.) in 15 c.c. of water were added. It was then heated under reflux

in a water-bath for about three hours, when voluminous precipitates separated from the reaction mixture in the form of tiny clusters. The compound was then filtered off from the mother-liquor while cold and crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid (50%) (animal charcoal), m. p. 251-53° (decomp.). It is practically insoluble in alcohol, water, acetic acid, benzene, and petroleum ether, and less soluble in a mixture of alcohol-water and alcohol-acetic acid. (Found: As, 11.75; Br, 25.63. $C_{21}H_{18}O_2N_2BrAs$ requires As, 11.96; Br, 25.51 per cent).

The other compounds were prepared in a similar way and are described in Table I.

TABLE I

Name of compound.	M. p.	Crystalline structure.	Solubility.	Analysis	
				Found.	Calc.
<i>p</i> -Arsono-aniline-malon-di- <i>p</i> -tolylamide $C_{22}H_{24}O_2N_2As$.	233° (decomp.)	Shining tiny crystals.	Insoluble in alcohol, water, acetic acid and less soluble in 50% mixture of alcohol and acetic acid.	As, 15.10% N, 8.62	15.13% 8.45
<i>p</i> -Arsono-aniline-malon-dibenzylamide. $C_{22}H_{22}O_2N_2As$.	266° (decomp.)	Tiny clusters.	Sparingly soluble in alcohol, water, acetic acid and soluble in 50% mixture of alcohol-water and alcohol-acetic acid.	As, 25.24 N, 8.36	25.13 8.45

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